

THE THEME OF SPACE IN THE NOVEL "PRIDE AND PREJUDICE" BY JANE AUSTEN

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Annotation: We intend to analyze the common features that, as a rule, are transmitted when defining localities and the attitude of women to them in various contexts. We chose Jane Austen's book *Pride and Prejudice* because it can demonstrate that all societies are experiencing the same or similar progress. I am trying to demonstrate that the character of a woman is constantly influenced by male (and, unfortunately, female) judgments, locality and social connections. Currently, our societies tend to attract their attention beyond their borders, which leads to infringement of women's rights and fear of ill-treatment.

Keywords: locality, woman, self-knowledge, contribution, literature, freedom.

It is interesting to observe the definition of the word "place" in relation to "person". Especially when it comes to "*Pride and Prejudice*", where Austin made extensive use of the technique of objective correlation, in which many, if not all, of her decorations largely reflect the characteristics of their owners. In addition, she uses several other techniques concerning the sense of place in her novel, which are important not only to facilitate numerous plot points, but also to establish and understand her characters and their relationships. So, what are these methods and why are they so effective? To find answers to such questions, we should take a closer look at Austen's methods of incorporating a sense of place into her novel.

The technique of objective correlation is often used to establish the qualities of a character by reflecting them in the environment of this character. These can be tangible objects, personal items, or, in Austin's case, locations. If we look at the setting of Rosings, we will see that it is described as ostentatious, overwhelming and, compared to Pemberley, another large country estate, quite flashy:

...From the lobby, to the beautiful proportions and finished decorations of which Mr. Collins enthusiastically pointed out, they followed servants... Despite the fact that Sir William had been to St. James's, he was so overwhelmed by the splendor surrounding him that he barely had the courage to return a very low

bow and take his seat without saying a word; and his daughter, scared almost to death, sat down on the edge of her chair, not knowing which way to look...

The intimidation of Sir William Lucas by the enormity of the world around him perfectly demonstrates the overly extravagant nature of Rosings, the description of which persists throughout this chapter, and the rest of the novel. At the center of this tastelessness we find Lady Catherine de Burgh, a creature exactly matching the nature of her surroundings. She is large, intimidating and self-centered, and it is interesting to note that both she and her estate cause a sense of discomfort to those who have the misfortune to be nearby.

She makes her visitors feel uncomfortable; on Elizabeth and in during Charlotte's first visit, it is described that "little could be done except to listen to Lady Catherine's speech, which she did without interruption until coffee was served, expressing her opinion on each issue in such a decisive manner that proved that she was not used to having her judgments challenged".

It is also interesting to note that Darcy Elizabeth's first sentence occurs in this uncomfortable environment, and after that both characters feel even worse than before. However, his second return to Longbourn, a place where Elizabeth feels comfortable, is more successful. Another famous estate in *Pride and Prejudice* will undoubtedly be Pemberley, Mr. Darcy's country estate. Compared to Rosings, although it is also large and majestic, its visitors have no sense of discomfort or any hint of flashiness: The rooms were tall and beautiful, and their furniture corresponded to the wealth of their owner, but Elizabeth noted with admiration his taste that the furniture was neither tasteless nor uselessly refined; there was less splendor and more real elegance in it than in the furniture of Rosings.

A similar description can be applied to Mr. Darcy himself. Although at first he seems proud and arrogant, in fact he is a decent guy, well-dressed (although not too spectacular) and very down-to-earth. Thanks to this description of Pemberley, we see Elizabeth's comfort in her surroundings (as opposed to her anxiety in Rosings), and once again, thanks to this reception, we can see (from what follows in the book) that she will be at ease with Mr. Darcy himself. Almost all the settings in *Pride and Prejudices* effectively reflect their owners: Longbourn House is relatively nondescript, similar to Mr. and Mrs. Bennet; Brighton, a bustling and flashy seaside town where Lydia finds herself with Wickham; and lesser-known places like Ramsgate, a quiet and isolated place in Kent, very similar to Georgiana Darcy herself.

In addition to using an objective correlate, Austin creates a sense of balance in his story due to the fact that several notable events occur outside, while other, less significant events occur inside. Events such as Darcy's delivery of Elizabeth's letter, numerous meetings, and his infamous second proposal occur during walks in the garden. This is most interesting because it is the events taking place in the vast open spaces of the garden that accumulate into important decisions concerning Elizabeth's future, at that time how less important events, such as Mr. Collins' proposal, occur within the inner recesses.

One might assume that these important events take place outside, since the garden is a place that everyone shares; a kind of common territory where there are no advantages, no disadvantages, or any influences. Openness in the fresh air contributes to a sense of honesty in those characters who happen to be there, and this feeling, therefore, affects the significance of these events in Elizabeth's future with Mr. Darcy. While inside, locked within the confines of the house, Elizabeth finds herself surrounded by the influence of her frivolous mother and trapped by Mr. Collins. This environment, far from openness and honesty, causes completely opposite feelings, which is why events such as his proposal have little effect on her life as a whole.

The sense of place also contributes to the development of several plot points, such as Lydia's escape with Mr. Wickham, Elizabeth's trip to Netherfield (where she makes her first-and indelible-impression on Caroline Bingley), along with many others. If it were not for these different places, the characters would not need to correspond through written communication, and the numerous letters that we find in *Pride and Prejudice* would have no meaning for existence. These letters (of which there are twenty novels in the book) give a great sense of personal insight into the essence of the characters, and since it is thanks to these means of communication that readers are able to distinguish between the feelings of one character to another, and in the case of Elizabeth and Jane - to feel almost as if we were reading entries in a diary, their relationship was so close.

It is interesting to note that the original title of *Pride and Prejudice* was "First Impressions" and may have been written entirely in epistolary form. If it wasn't for the feeling, of course, there would be no letters in general, and we would have had a really very insipid story. It is also noteworthy that with all these correspondences of important information, the responses of the characters can never be spontaneous (with the exception of Elizabeth; it is often heard how she responds to letters as if she were really addressing the author).

The very nature of writing requires that feelings be they are thought out before they are put on paper, and therefore, when deciding important issues (for example, what should be done with Lydia's escape with Mr. Wickham), each party should first think about what is right to say, and thus eliminate any sense of spontaneity.

This allows many other events to occur, such as misunderstandings between characters, and delays most of the action, ensuring that mistakes cannot be fixed immediately. For example, if Jane and Elizabeth were constantly in the same place, the latter would simply She would have been able to tell Jane about her misconceptions about Miss Bingley, and most of this storyline would have been lost.

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References:

1. Нуридинова М. Ж. ПОСТМОДЕРНИЧНОСТЬ РОМАНА А. БИТОВА «ПУШКИНСКИЙ ДОМ» //Ученый XXI века. – 2022. – №. 2 (83). – С. 34-37.
2. Нуридинова М. ТЕМА ПРОСТРАНСТВА В РОМАНЕ «ГОРДОСТЬ И ПРЕДУБЕЖДЕНИЕ» ДЖЕЙНА ОСТИНА //Innovations in Technology and Science Education. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 15. – С. 384-391.
3. Jurayevna N. M. Style, Holistic Consideration of a Work of Art and the Problem of Selective Analysis in Russian Literature //Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 223-229.
4. Jurayevna N. M. THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN A RUSSIAN LITERARY TEXT //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 81-84.
5. 5.1. Рустамовна М.Г. Представление синонимов в толковых словарях узбекского языка //Среднеевропейский научный вестник. – 2020. – Т. 6. – С. 117-120.
6. Mirxanova G. R. et al. SYNTACTIC ANALYSIS OF WORKS OF ART IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS: METHODS AND APPLICATIONS. – 2023.
7. Nilufar A. G 'IJDUVON SHEVASIDAGI AYRIM SO 'ZLARINING "DEVONU LUG 'OTIT TURK" ASARIDA IFODALANISHI //UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 219-225.
8. Latipova S. JO 'RA FOZIL IJODIDA XALQ MAQOLLARINING O 'RNI //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 18. – С. 92-96.
9. Bafoyeva N. TRANSLATION DIFFICULTIES OF ABDULLA KAHNAR 'S ESSAY "THIEF" INTO ENGLISH //Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 05. – С. 60-63.
10. SHE'RIYAT–RUHIYATKO 'ZGUSI. M Farmonova, PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS, 2022.
11. Gafurova D. K. FORMATION OF FLUID SPEECH IN PRESCHOOLERS //International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. – 2021. – Т. 6. – №. 1. – С. 5-5.
12. Гафурова Д. Х., Курбанова М. Ф. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ БЕГЛОЙ РЕЧИ У ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ ПУТЁМ ЧТЕНИЯ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ //Проблемы науки. – 2021. – С. 81.
13. Rajabova M. ЮСУФ АМИРИЙ-МАҲОРАТЛИ ШОИР //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2023. – Т. 34. – №. 34.

14. Kizi R. G. B., Ubaydullayevna N. Y., Kizi M. M. I. The Image of Trees in Folklore: Genesis and Poetic Interpretations //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 04.
15. Бахроновна Р. Г. ИСТОРИКОМИФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОБРАЗОВ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ДЕРЕВЬЯМИ В ФОЛЬКЛОРЕ //WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS: сборник статей ЛII Международной научнопрактической конференции. – 2021. – Т. 52. – С. 1,157-160.
16. Nuridinova M.J., Rustamova A.A., Sattorova M.S. INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA YOZISHNI O'QITISHDA INTEGRATSION YUNDASHISHLARI // Jahon fani. – 2020. – yo'q. 1 (34). - S. 76-78.